

Radioisotopes for RTGs from MOX-Fueled Lead-Cooled Fast Reactors

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803456

ABSTRACT

Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generators (RTGs) employ long-lived radioisotopes to provide reliable power in space and remote environments. This work quantifies the production of key radioisotopes – ^{241}Am , ^{90}Sr , and ^{238}Pu – in Lead-Cooled Fast Reactors (LFRs) using Mixed Oxide (MOX) fuel. The LFR fuel cycle produces ^{238}Pu through irradiation of ^{237}Np , while ^{241}Am and ^{90}Sr can be obtained from spent fuel. The fission product ^{90}Sr is obtained in higher quantities than in thermal reactors at the same power output, while ^{241}Am is produced more efficiently in thermal reactors. In contrast, ^{238}Pu is more effectively produced by placing targets outside the LFR core and limiting irradiation time. Both ^{90}Sr and ^{241}Am are shown to be produced in quantities suitable for RTGs.

Keywords: Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generators, Lead-Cooled Fast Reactors, Radioisotope production

1. INTRODUCTION

A Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator (RTG) converts heat from radioactive decay into electricity exploiting the Seebeck effect, where a temperature difference across thermoelectric materials generates a voltage and drives an electric current [1]. It uses long-lived isotopes with low gamma/neutron emissions and a high rate of heat deposition, enclosing them in thermoelectric couples (e.g., Bi_2Te_3 , PbTe [2]) and protective housing. Despite their low efficiency (5–9%), RTGs have been used for decades to provide reliable, low-maintenance power for space missions and remote sites. Current research focuses on improving isotope production methods and enhancing thermoelectric conversion efficiency to increase RTG performance [3].

An opportunity to enhance the supply of radioisotopes for RTGs lies in their production within advanced nuclear systems, e.g. Lead-cooled Fast Reactors (LFRs) using Mixed Oxide (MOX) fuel currently being developed by newcleo. This work investigates the magnitude of isotope production in LFRs to support RTG supply, and compares it with production in thermal reactors. Such production contributes to waste management and actinides recycling, enabling long-duration power supply. The paper briefly reviews RTG history, working principles, and fuel selection criteria in Sec. 2, and then evaluates isotope production in LFRs with MOX fuel, focusing on ^{241}Am , ^{90}Sr , and ^{238}Pu in Sec. 3. Conclusion follows in Sec. 4.

2. RADIOISOTOPE THERMOELECTRIC GENERATORS

RTGs were first developed in the late 1950s by the U.S. Atomic Energy Commission to provide long-lasting and maintenance-free power in remote areas. Their first use in space was on the Transit 4A satellite in 1961, establishing RTGs as reliable power sources for deep-space missions. They have been essential power sources for key missions including Apollo, Viking, Voyager, Cassini, New Horizons, and Mars rovers [4]. On Earth, RTGs were used in the late 20th century to supply power to remote lighthouses, weather stations, and navigation beacons in isolated regions such as the Arctic and Siberia, demonstrating their versatility in harsh environments.

Thermoelectric conversion in RTGs relies on the Seebeck effect, where a temperature gradient across semiconductors generates an electromotive force (EMF). This temperature gradient arises between a hot side, heated by

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the energy released in radioactive decay, and a cold side. A thermoelectric generator (TEG) is installed between the hot and cold sides. It consists of multiple thermopiles, each a p- and n-type couple, connected electrically in series and thermally in parallel, i.e. experiencing the same thermal gradient. The temperature gradient causes charge carriers, holes in p-type and electrons in n-type, to diffuse from the hot side to the cold side, leading to charge separation and voltage generation [1], see Fig. 1. When the load is connected, this voltage drives a current through the external circuit.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the thermoelectric generator.

2.1. Heat source

The performance of RTGs strongly depends on the choice of the radioactive fuel releasing thermal power. The selection of suitable isotopes is typically based on the following requirements:

1. High power density, which is achieved for isotopes with high decay energy and high activity.
2. The half-life should be long enough to ensure continuous and sufficient energy during the RTG's lifetime of a few decades, while still being short enough to obtain relatively high activity.
3. Low gamma and neutron emission, minimizing shielding requirements and the mass of the RTG system.
4. Reasonable availability and production cost.

For these reasons, alpha-emitting isotopes are generally preferred over beta emitters for space RTGs, as they combine high energy release per decay with relatively low associated radiation hazards. These advantages, however, are less critical for terrestrial applications.

The most important isotopes that fulfill these requirements are ^{238}Pu , ^{241}Am , and ^{90}Sr [5]. These were used in the past and are still considered for future applications. Their key properties are summarized in Table I. The quantities presented are related by $P = E_D \lambda N_A / M$ where P is the specific decay heat (power per unit mass), E_D is the decay energy per emission, λ is the decay constant, N_A is Avogadro's number and M is the molar mass. In MOX-fuelled LFRs, ^{241}Am and ^{90}Sr , which is a fission product, can be obtained from spent fuel and ^{238}Pu can be obtained from the irradiation of ^{237}Np which is inserted in the reactor.

Current research on RTGs explores the use of ^{90}Sr and ^{241}Am , in addition to ^{238}Pu , as radioisotopes in RTGs. The use of ^{90}Sr and ^{241}Am is planned by Zeno Power, in collaboration with NASA, and by the European Space Agency in collaboration with academic partners. Planned projects focus on space and satellite applications.

Table I. Summary of the key properties of the isotopes.

Isotopes	Emission	Half-life [y]	Decay Energy per Emission [MeV]	Decay Heat [W/g]
^{238}Pu	α	87.74	5.593	0.567
^{241}Am	α	432.2	5.638	0.114
^{90}Sr	β	28.78	1.131	0.925

3. ISOTOPE PRODUCTION IN LFR WITH MOX FUEL

LFRs using MOX fuel provide a fast neutron spectrum, leading to transmutation rates and isotope accumulation that differ from thermal reactors, traditionally used for RTG isotope production. It is therefore important to evaluate isotope production in LFRs in detail, identifying the most efficient production mechanisms and understanding the underlying physics. Our results are relevant for any fast reactors that have a similar neutron spectrum. Fig. 2

shows the neutron LFR flux spectrum used, which was calculated internally in Monte Carlo simulations, both inside the core and outside it, as well as the flux of a typical PWR reactor, taken from the FISPACT-II Wiki [6].

To calculate the number of radioisotopes during irradiation and cooling, one needs to solve the Bateman equation, a set of differential equations that describe the gain and loss in number of isotopes due to reactions and radioactive decay. The equation can be solved analytically for simplified decay chains or numerically for full decay chains using a nuclear inventory code such as FISPACT-II [6]. When possible, both approaches are used in this work to verify calculations, with final results coming from FISPACT-II. Evaluated nuclear data libraries are employed to ensure accurate modeling, using ENDF/B-VIII.0 for cross sections, fission yields, and decay data. FISPACT furthermore employs self-shielding corrections for cross sections, for which TENDL-2017 probability tables are used. For ^{241}Am and ^{90}Sr , the power is held constant during depletion to reproduce the settings in the core of a reactor. Meanwhile for ^{238}Pu , the neutron flux is kept constant, since the presence of ^{237}Np fission affects the power normalization, making it unfeasible to keep the power constant. The simulations thus describes an irradiation probe filled with ^{237}Np , subjected to constant flux. A parametric study varying fresh fuel composition and power is conducted in all cases to evaluate how these parameters influence isotope production. The thermal power density had a default value of 335 W/cm^3 , and it was varied from 140 W/cm^3 to 560 W/cm^3 , where the high value is used as a limit condition. In the composition of the MOX fuel, the amount of UO_2 was varied from 70 to 80 %, and the amount of ^{241}Am in the total plutonium and americium content was varied from 2 to 8 %. Additionally, a comparison with a Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) is performed under the same power, irradiation time, and the same initial fuel composition to compare isotope evolution. Table II lists the default initial composition of a fuel assembly in the calculations.

Table II. Composition of fresh fuel used for FISPACT calculations. All fractions are mass fractions.

Oxide	%	Pu	%	U	%	O	%
UO_2	79	^{238}Pu	2.6	^{234}U	0.00052	^{16}O	99.76
PuO_2	21	^{239}Pu	54.5	^{235}U	0.19	^{17}O	0.04
		^{240}Pu	25.9	^{238}U	99.809	^{18}O	0.2
		^{241}Pu	7.3				
		^{242}Pu	5.7				
		^{241}Am	4.0				

Figure 2. Neutron spectra used for FISPACT calculations.

3.1. ^{90}Sr

^{90}Sr is produced in significant quantities as a fission product in nuclear reactors, as it has a high cumulative fission yield. Most of the ^{90}Sr found in spent fuel is not produced directly, but rather through the decay of short-lived precursors, ^{90}Br (half-life 1.95 s), ^{90}Kr (32 s), ^{90}Rb (2.6 min) and its metastable state, $^{90\text{m}}\text{Rb}$ (4.3 min), which are themselves formed during fission. These isotopes decay in succession via beta emission to ultimately yield ^{90}Sr , which accumulates during the reactor operation. As an example, the simplest decay chain is $X \xrightarrow{\text{fiss.}} ^{90}\text{Sr}$ while the one with the most intermediate steps is $X \xrightarrow{\text{fiss.}} ^{90}\text{Br} \xrightarrow[74.7\%]{\beta^-} ^{90}\text{Kr} \xrightarrow{\beta^-} ^{90\text{m}}\text{Rb} \xrightarrow[97.4\%]{\beta^-} ^{90}\text{Sr}$.

A simple model for the production of ^{90}Sr comes from making three assumptions. Firstly, it is assumed that all beta decays happen instantaneously, which is justified for time scales longer than a few minutes. Secondly, it is assumed that the density of actinides does not change substantially during irradiation. This is justified when irradiation lasts less than a few years. Thirdly, the decay of ^{90}Sr (half-life of 29 years) is ignored, which is justified

for time scales of a few years. The yield of ^{90}Sr at time t is then

$$N_{90\text{Sr}} = t \sum_X \sum_j N_X(t=0) R_{X,\text{fiss.}} f_{X \rightarrow i} p_{i \rightarrow 90\text{Sr}} \quad (1)$$

where $N_X(t=0)$ is the initial number of actinide X , $R_{X,\text{fiss.}} = \int dE \sigma_{X,\text{fiss.}} \phi$ is its reaction rate for fission, $f_{X \rightarrow i}$ is the yield of fission product i , where i is one of ^{90}Sr , ^{90}Rb , $^{90\text{m}}\text{Rb}$, ^{90}Kr , ^{90}Br , and $p_{i \rightarrow 90\text{Sr}}$ is the probability that i decays into ^{90}Sr . The flux ϕ for both LFR and PWR is normalized so that the power density is fixed as $P/V = \sum_X \int dE k_X(E) \phi(E) N_X$, where k_X is the kerma factor for actinide X . This model has been compared with FISPACT simulations. The discrepancy is less than 15% for the parameters in this study which is reasonable given the assumptions used. Results in this section come from FISPACT simulations but they will be interpreted in light of Eq. (1). The results are nearly independent of the power level of the reactor when they are expressed in terms of burnup.

The production of ^{90}Sr depends on reactor conditions and the cooling time after extraction from the reactor. Fig. 3 shows the temporal evolution of ^{90}Sr atoms during reactor operation and subsequent cooling in LFR and PWR with the same power output. During the irradiation phase, the inventory of ^{90}Sr increases steadily due to its continuous production as a fission product. When the fuel assembly is removed from the reactor, the ^{90}Sr inventory begins to decline slowly due to its radioactive decay. The modest decrease over time reflects its relatively long half-life of 28.8 years, indicating that a substantial fraction of the produced inventory remains available for recovery even after extended cooling. Based on the ^{90}Sr inventory contained in the irradiated fuel assemblies, it is possible to

Figure 3. ^{90}Sr evolution in an LFR and a PWR at 335 W/cm^3 of thermal power density, with composition given in Table II. Here m_{Sr90} is the mass of the ^{90}Sr produced and m_{fuel} is the total mass of actinides in the fresh fuel.

estimate the number of RTGs that can be supplied. The extracted ^{90}Sr is assumed to be converted into SrTiO_3 with a chemical conversion efficiency of 95% [9]. Considering a thermoelectric conversion efficiency of 7% for the RTG [3], the number of RTGs that can be fueled from a single spent fuel assembly with fuel mass of 110 kg (including oxygen) are 15 for a 30 W RTG (such as SNAP23 [3]) and 4 for a 100 W RTG (such as Sentinel100 [3]).

Fig. 3 shows that a similar amount of ^{90}Sr can be produced in LFR and PWR at the same power, with slightly higher values for LFR. These results carry considerable theoretical uncertainty due to uncertainty in the fission yields, $f_{X \rightarrow i}$. As an example, the fission yields used for ^{239}Pu have a relative uncertainty between 10% and 60% in the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library. Besides, similar results can be obtained with different libraries, with the ^{90}Sr production varying of about 3% in a fast reactor using fission yields from JENDL-5 instead of ENDF/B-VIII.0. In the analytic model, the higher production in LFR reactors is due to a complicated interplay between the reaction rate of fission and the fission yields. The total rate of fission is about the same in LFR and PWR, as the release of energy by fission does not vary much and the power is kept constant. However, the nuclides that give fission are different in the two cases, as shown in Table III. Among the main fissile and fertile isotopes, ^{238}U exhibits the highest cumulative fission yield for ^{90}Sr . Because ^{238}U contributes a larger fraction of fissions in LFRs than in PWRs, the overall production of ^{90}Sr is correspondingly higher in LFRs.

	Fraction of fission in LFR	Fraction of fission in PWR	Total fission yield of ^{90}Sr
^{239}Pu	71 %	89 %	0.020
^{238}U	10 %	2 %	0.029
^{240}Pu	7 %	1 %	0.017
^{241}Pu	6 %	6 %	0.015

Table III. Contribution of different actinides in the fuel to fission, and the total fission yield of ^{90}Sr , $\sum_i f_{X \rightarrow i} p_{i \rightarrow ^{90}\text{Sr}}$. The total fission yield is the same in the LFR and in the PWR, to the accuracy shown here.

The production of ^{90}Sr in a LFR has been studied parametrically, focusing on the effects of MOX fuel composition and reactor power on its accumulation. The parametric study shows that increasing the reactor power results in slightly higher ^{90}Sr production at the same maximum burnup. At lower power, longer irradiation allows more decay of ^{90}Sr , reducing the net accumulation. As an example the amount of ^{90}Sr atoms after an irradiation with a final burnup of 67 MWd/kg is 14 % higher in a reactor with a thermal power density of 560 W/cm³ than in a reactor with a power density of 140 W/cm³. The time evolution curves of ^{90}Sr atoms for various U-Pu and Am-Pu ratios in the initial MOX composition show discrepancy of less than 3 % across the composition range specified at the beginning of Sec. 3, indicating that within the examined range, changes in minor actinide content do not substantially alter the ^{90}Sr inventory.

3.2. ^{238}Pu

^{238}Pu is produced by irradiating ^{237}Np targets in high-flux reactors, forming ^{238}Np , which decays to ^{238}Pu and is then chemically separated. This complex, costly process of chemical separation is limited to few facilities due to technical challenges. For the production of the ^{237}Np needed, see [7].

We model the decay chain as

where we label the nuclides A , B and C to simplify the notation. The decay of A and C can be neglected for short exposure times. This can be expressed in equations as

$$\frac{dN_A}{dt} = -R_A N_A; \quad \frac{dN_B}{dt} = -\lambda N_B + R_{A,(n,\gamma)} N_A; \quad \frac{dN_C}{dt} = -R_C N_C + \lambda N_B. \quad (3)$$

where $R_A = \int dE \bar{\sigma}_A \phi$ is a condensed microscopic reaction rate and $\bar{\sigma}_A$ is the sum of all non-scattering microscopic partial cross sections, i.e. all partial cross sections that change the species of the nuclide, and similarly for C . The sum of all non-scattering partial cross sections was evaluated as the total cross section (MT=1), with elastic (MT=2) and inelastic (MT=4) partial cross sections subtracted. Furthermore, $R_{A,(n,\gamma)} = \int dE \sigma_{A,(n,\gamma)} \phi$ is the reaction rate for the (n, γ) reaction and λ is the decay constant of ^{238}Np . The non-scattering partial cross sections of ^{238}Np can be neglected for the flux considered because of the isotope's short half-life of 2.10 days. Eq. (3) can be solved analytically to give

$$N_C(t) = \frac{N_{A0} \lambda R_{A,(n,\gamma)}}{\lambda - R_A} \left[\frac{e^{-\lambda t}}{\lambda - R_C} - \frac{e^{-R_A t}}{R_A - R_C} \right] + \frac{N_{A0} \beta R_{A,(n,\gamma)}}{(\lambda - R_C)(R_A - R_C)} e^{-R_C t} \quad (4)$$

where only A is present in the initial condition with number N_{A0} . The accuracy of this analytical solution was checked by comparing it with FISPACT-II. The discrepancy is always below 3 % for the parameters used in this study. Results from FISPACT simulations are thus shown but they are interpreted in light of the analytic model.

	$R_{(n,\gamma)} (\times 10^{-9} s^{-1})$	$R_A (\times 10^{-9} s^{-1})$	$R_C (\times 10^{-9} s^{-1})$
LFR, in-core	2.8	3.4	3.0
PWR	2.7	2.8	1.3
LFR, ex-core	6.4	6.5	2.3

Table IV. Condensed microscopic reaction rates in an LFR, inside and outside the core, and in an PWR. The first two columns are for ^{237}Np and the last one for ^{238}Pu .

Fig. 4 shows the evolution of ^{238}Pu inside the core of an LFR and for an averaged flux outside the core, as well as inside the core of a PWR for a given initial amount of ^{237}Np . For consistency of comparison, the flux of the PWR and the LFR inside the core were normalized so that they give the same power density for the MOX fuel in Table II. The flux outside the LFR core was furthermore normalized with the same normalization factor as the flux inside the core. The condensed flux per volume outside the LFR core is nevertheless much lower, being only 16 % of that in-core.

The main result of Fig. 4 is that after irradiation of ^{237}Np for 5.6 years outside the LFR core, 52 % of the neptunium has been transformed into ^{238}Pu . This conversion rate is around 60 % higher than inside the core of LFR or PWR. To understand the higher efficiency of transmutation outside the LFR core, we compare the reaction rates in Eq. (4) for the three different fluxes, see Table IV. The important difference is the higher rate of (n, γ) reactions of ^{237}Np for the location outside the LFR core than for the other two cases. This higher value of $R_{A,(n,\gamma)}$ means that ^{237}Np transmutes more quickly to ^{238}Np , which then decays fast into ^{238}Pu . The reason for the higher value of $R_{A,(n,\gamma)}$ outside the LFR core lays in a softer neutron spectrum, see Fig. 2. We note that non-scattering reaction rate of ^{237}Np , R_A , is also higher outside the core in the LFR reactor, see Table IV, but it includes (n, γ) reactions and can be interpreted in the same way. These results do not depend on the power of the reactor, as long as the same level of burnup is held. For a different fuel composition, the flux only changes very slightly and the yield of ^{238}Pu through irradiation stays nearly the same. The Fispact simulations show that additionally ^{239}Pu is created in neutron capture of ^{238}Pu and constitutes around 10 % of the total plutonium at discharge burnup. On the contrary, ^{236}Pu (which is created in $(n,2n)$ reactions of ^{237}Np) and its decay product ^{232}U , which is a very hard gamma emitter, are only present in trace quantities of less than one part in trillion.

Figure 4. ^{238}Pu evolution inside and outside the core of LFR and inside the core of PWR. The fraction of irradiated ^{237}Np nuclei that has been transmuted to ^{238}Pu is shown.

3.3. ^{241}Am

^{241}Am is obtained as a byproduct of plutonium decay, in particular by beta decay of ^{241}Pu . During irradiation, the densities of ^{241}Pu and ^{241}Am change as they are partially consumed by neutron fission and capture. Finally, ^{241}Am is recovered by reprocessing spent fuel. It should be noted that ^{241}Am is normally already present in the fresh fuel, either due to the decay of ^{241}Pu or due to it being added as burnable poison. The ^{241}Am should not be

extracted from the fresh fuel, which would affect overall reactor performance.

The availability of ^{241}Am in spent fuel depends on reactor operating conditions and cooling time. Fig. 5 illustrates the evolution of ^{241}Am and ^{241}Pu density during irradiation and subsequent cooling in LFR and PWR after extraction from the reactor. The irradiation period of 2040 days at a power level of 335 W/cm^3 is followed by 1610 days of cooling. In LFR, during reactor operation, ^{241}Am accumulates as ^{241}Pu decays, but its density is strongly reduced by neutron-induced fission and capture reactions that consume it. Therefore the overall inventory decreases during the irradiation period. After discharge, ^{241}Am concentration starts to gradually increase due to the only decay of ^{241}Pu . Thanks to its long half-life of 432 years, a significant amount remains available for recovery even after extended cooling times.

Fig. 5 shows a very different behaviour in the evolution of ^{241}Pu during irradiation between a fast and a thermal reactor. Whereas the number of ^{241}Pu nuclei decreases during irradiation in LFR, it increases substantially in the PWR reactor. It is difficult to reproduce exactly this evolution with a simple analytic model since all isotopes of Pu with mass number lower than 241 can be transformed into ^{241}Pu by successive neutron capture events, meaning that a large system of ODEs must be solved. Therefore, only FISPACT-II results are discussed in this section. Nevertheless, the differences between LFR and PWR shown in Fig. 5 can easily be understood by looking at the reaction rates. The (n, γ) reaction rate that transforms ^{240}Pu into ^{241}Pu is $8.6 \cdot 10^{-10}\text{ s}^{-1}$ for LFR against $5.9 \cdot 10^{-9}$ for PWR, that is a nearly seven times higher value. At the same time, the rate of nonelastic reactions that transform ^{241}Pu into other nuclides is more similar between the two reactors, $5.0 \cdot 10^{-9}\text{ s}^{-1}$ for LFR and $8.4 \cdot 10^{-9}$ for PWR. This means that ^{240}Pu transmutes much more efficiently into ^{241}Pu in PWR than in LFR, while ^{241}Pu is transmuted only moderately more effectively in PWR than in LFR.

Figure 5. ^{241}Am and ^{241}Pu evolution in one fuel assembly of LFR and PWR at 335 W/cm^3 of thermal power. $N_{0, \text{Pu}241}$ is the initial number of ^{241}Pu nuclei.

Figure 6. Mass of ^{241}Am extracted with different strategies. It is shown as a fraction of m_{fuel} , the total mass of actinides in the fresh fuel.

Two extraction strategies are considered for obtaining ^{241}Am from the spent fuel in an LFR: (1) reprocessing spent fuel to extract accumulated ^{241}Am directly but this is complicated by the presence of other isotopes of americium; and (2) isolating plutonium from spent fuel to let ^{241}Pu decay into ^{241}Am , avoiding the presence of other isotopes of americium at the cost of longer cooling and extra separation. Fig. 6 shows the mass of ^{241}Am extracted with these two strategies, using the same composition of fresh fuel.

In case 1, the presence of ^{243}Am , which comes from the decay of ^{243}Pu and which is present in recovered americium, reduces suitability for use in RTGs. Most importantly, ^{243}Am has lower specific power than ^{241}Am , and thus reduces the overall power density of the source. Although it emits little gamma radiation, its spontaneous fission increases neutron output and shielding needs. Additionally, the long half-life of ^{243}Am (7370 years) causes the radioactivity of the RTG to persist for extended periods, creating safety concerns. For all the reasons the minimization of ^{243}Am is important for safe, efficient RTG design. In case 1, ^{243}Am accumulates over time as ^{243}Pu decays, reducing purity. This ^{243}Am is impossible to separate chemically from ^{241}Am . As example after 10 years from the extraction the fraction of ^{243}Am is 11 % of the total americium. In contrast, case 2 limits this by allowing ^{243}Pu , which has a half-life of five hours, to decay before separation. While the total RTG yield is lower, this approach ensures good isotopic purity and presents the best strategy.

The calculated ^{241}Am inventory for case 2 allows estimating the number of RTGs that can be fueled. It is assumed that 95 % of the extracted ^{241}Am is converted into AmO_2 [8]. and that the thermoelectric conversion efficiency of the RTG is 7 %. In that case, with extraction of ^{241}Am happening 20 years after irradiation and cooling, from a single fuel assembly that originally had 110 kg of fresh fuel (including the oxygen), one can extract ^{241}Am for around 2 RTGs of $P_{el} = 100\text{ W}$ (such as MMRTG [3]) and around 1 RTG of $P_{el} = 150\text{ W}$ (such as MHW [3]).

Focusing then on case 2, a parametric study of ^{241}Pu evolution in LFR is made by varying the initial MOX fuel composition and reactor thermal power. Considering the relative variation of ^{241}Pu , changing the plutonium and uranium dioxide percentages does not significantly affect the evolution of ^{241}Am . However, increasing the initial amount of ^{241}Am relative to ^{241}Pu decreases the depletion of ^{241}Pu , but this is mainly due to the lower initial amount of ^{241}Pu and the reduced neutron availability caused by ^{241}Am absorption. Additionally, reactor power was varied while reaching the same maximum burnup. At low thermal power, the longer irradiation time results in more decay of ^{241}Pu atoms. In contrast, higher power results in shorter irradiation periods and therefore less depletion. As an example the amount of ^{241}Pu atoms after an irradiation with a final burnup of 67 MWd/kg is 40 % higher in a reactor with a power density of 560 W/cm^3 than in a reactor with a power density of 140 W/cm^3 .

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, among the isotopes analyzed, ^{90}Sr and ^{238}Pu emerge as the most favorable candidates for RTG radioisotopes extracted from LFR operation. ^{90}Sr can be retrieved from LFR spent fuel and has higher production levels than in PWRs due the high cumulative fission yield of ^{90}Sr from ^{238}U fission. ^{90}Sr can be separated from the spent fuel in a simple fashion within established reprocessing techniques. Conversely, ^{238}Pu is created during irradiation of ^{237}Np samples, either inside or outside the reactor core. ^{238}Pu production is substantially more efficient outside the LFR core than in PWR, due to a higher rate of neutron capture of ^{237}Np . However, challenges remain in the use of ^{238}Pu due to radiotoxicity, complex separation, and limited ^{237}Np supply. These factors make ^{90}Sr the most practical and efficient option for recovery in current fuel cycle scenarios, with ^{238}Pu also being an interesting candidate. In contrast, extraction of ^{241}Am from spent fuel is more favorable from PWRs than LFRs due to the higher content of ^{241}Pu that can be obtained thanks to the thermal neutron spectrum.

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